

HYBRID 1D CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK AND FUZZY CLUSTERING FOR DAMAGE DETECTION IN COMPOSITE PLATES USING LASER ULTRASONIC GUIDED WAVES

Shain Azadi^{1,2}, Yoji Okabe² and Valter Carvelli¹

¹Department A.B.C., Politecnico di Milano
Piazza Leonardo da Vinci 32, 20133, Milano, Italy
Email: shain.azadi@polimi.it, valter.carvelli@polimi.it,

²Institute of Industrial Science, The University of Tokyo
4-6-1 Komaba Meguro-ku, 153-8505, Tokyo, Japan
Email: okabey@iis.u-tokyo.ac.jp,

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a hybrid learning framework for structural health monitoring (SHM) of composite laminates using laser ultrasonic guided waves (LUGWs) with limited labelled data. A lightweight one-dimensional convolutional neural network (1D-CNN) is trained on a small, spatially labelled subset to extract low-dimensional latent features from raw waveforms. These features are clustered using five classical algorithms (K-Means, GMM, BGMM, DBSCAN, and HDBSCAN) and a novel method, namely Probabilistic CNN-Fuzzy Clustering (PCFC). PCFC integrates CNN-derived class probabilities with fuzzy membership values from the Fuzzy C-Means algorithm, thereby enabling soft, uncertainty-aware clustering in the latent space. The quality of the clustering is evaluated through spatial cluster map reconstructions, with PCFC consistently producing coherent and physically meaningful clusters that are aligned with known delamination regions. In the latent feature space, Principal Component Analysis reveals a consistent separation between damaged and undamaged waveforms along the first principal component, thus offering an interpretable indicator of damage severity. The proposed approach has the potential to reduce annotation requirements by an order of magnitude and mitigate the limitations of fully supervised learning. It offers a scalable and interpretable solution for reliable damage detection in composite structures, particularly in scenarios where comprehensive labelling is impractical.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon-fibre-reinforced polymer (CFRP) laminates are widely employed in aerospace, aviation, automotive, constructions, and wind energy applications due to their high specific stiffness, strength, and resistance to corrosion [1]. However, their layered architecture renders them inherently susceptible to inter-ply delamination, an internal defect that reduces load-bearing capacity, degrades stiffness, and introduces stress concentrations [2]. Because delaminations are not externally visible, inspection relies on non-destructive evaluation (NDE) techniques.

Ultrasonic guided waves (UGWs) offer high sensitivity to subsurface damage and enable large-area inspection from a single excitation point, making them well-suited for volumetric structural health monitoring (SHM) [3]. When generated by pulsed lasers, UGWs can propagate into the structure without contact and maintain performance on curved or thermally challenging surfaces, enabling inspection in environments where conventional methods may fail [4]. However, the interpretation of UGW signals typically requires expert domain knowledge, a process that is both time-consuming and costly.

To reduce reliance on manual interpretation, deep learning has been increasingly applied to UGW data [5]. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs), trained on two-dimensional (2D) wavefield images or time-frequency representations, can achieve high classification accuracy. Nevertheless, these approaches often require substantial preliminary processing (e.g., windowing, padding, or wavelet

transforms) and comprise numerous parameters, which hinders implementation on hardware platforms with limited resource [6].

One-dimensional CNNs (1D-CNNs) provide a more lightweight alternative, particularly suited to sequential data such as raw UGW signals. Convolution along the temporal axis enables 1D-CNNs to perform joint feature extraction and classification in a single, low-complexity pipeline. In comparison to their 2D counterparts, 1D-CNNs reduce the number of parameters by approximately an order of magnitude, thereby lowering computational overhead, reducing the risk of overfitting, and enabling real-time inference on consumer-grade hardware [7]. These characteristics render 1D-CNNs especially well-suited to onboard anomaly detection, a process characterised by the constraints of rapid inference and the scarcity of labelled data [8].

Despite their efficiency, even compact supervised models require fully labelled datasets that capture variation in sensor placement, laminate geometry, and damage morphology. These conditions are often impractical to reproduce comprehensively. The labelling of laser-ultrasonic datasets may involve destructive sectioning, micro-CT imaging, or artificial defect insertion. These processes are often labour-intensive and lack scalability, particularly in the context of rare or interacting damage modes. Consequently, the utilisation of supervised models that have been trained on limited labels renders them susceptible to overfitting and may impede their capacity to generalize to unseen conditions [9].

Unsupervised learning provides a complementary strategy by means of the identification of latent structure in unlabelled UGW data. Clustering and anomaly detection techniques, including K-Means, Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN), Hierarchical DBSCAN (HDBSCAN), Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM), and Bayesian GMM (BGMM) [10], have been employed to extract damage-related patterns without requiring prior annotation. These approaches are especially valuable when damage signatures are poorly defined, heterogeneous, or too numerous to label manually. Nevertheless, a persistent limitation remains: the resulting clusters often lack direct physical meaning and require post hoc interpretation to map to damage mechanisms. This interpretation step is subjective and prone to error, especially when defects are subtle or interact in complex ways.

To address these challenges, this paper proposes a hybrid learning framework that combines supervised and unsupervised learning. A compact 1D-CNN (~93,000 parameters) [11] is first trained on approximately 10% of the dataset using spatially defined labels. Subsequent to the training phase, the SoftMax classification head is eliminated, and the network is repurposed as an encoder that maps each input waveform to a 128-dimensional latent embedding. This embedding enhances class separability while suppressing nuisance variability.

Clustering algorithms, including K-Means, GMM, DBSCAN, HDBSCAN, and a novel Probabilistic CNN–Fuzzy Clustering (PCFC) method, are then applied in the latent space. These algorithms result in the generation of spatially coherent clusters that exhibit a high degree of alignment with delamination regions, without requiring additional supervision. The anchoring of the latent space with a small, labelled subset, is a key aspect of the framework, as it preserves physical interpretability, enables probabilistic associations with known damage states, and leverages the diversity of unlabelled data to improve generalization.

The objective of this work is to demonstrate that incorporating a limited amount of labelled data can significantly enhance the physical interpretability of clustering outcomes, and that the proposed PCFC method outperforms five state-of-the-art clustering algorithms when evaluated under a consistent neural architecture. The resulting workflow reduces annotation requirements by an order of magnitude, remains computationally efficient for embedded implementation, and addresses the supervision bottleneck that has hindered the adoption of deep learning in operational SHM systems.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 details specimen fabrication, laser-ultrasonic data acquisition, and the hybrid learning pipeline. Section 3 presents clustering results, spatial reconstructions, and an encoder ablation study. Section 4 concludes with key findings and directions for future work.

2 HYBRID LEARNING METHODOLOGY

2.1. Specimen Preparation and Laser Ultrasonic Data Acquisition

Eight-ply cross-ply CFRP laminates with a $[90_2/0_2]_s$ stacking sequence were fabricated using Toray T700SC/2500 prepreg [12]. Each plate measured $200 \times 200 \text{ mm}^2$ with a nominal thickness of 1.12 mm (0.14 mm per ply). Nine plates contained centrally embedded square Teflon inserts to simulate delaminations of 5×5 , 10×10 , or $20 \times 20 \text{ mm}^2$, located at three interlaminar depths (0.28, 0.56, and 0.84 mm), while one plate served as an undamaged control. Laminates were cured in a vacuum hot-press at 0.08 MPa and consolidated at a pressure of 8.6 MPa and a temperature of $130 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 hours, ensuring consistent fibre wet-out and minimal void content. The central insert placement suppressed edge effects and enabled a controlled matrix of size–depth combinations for waveform-to-damage analysis.

Laser-induced UGWs (LUGWs) were generated using a non-contact Laser Ultrasonic Visualization Inspector (LUVI-CP1, Tsukuba Technology), employing a 1064 nm, 10 ns Nd:YAG laser pulse focused to a 0.25 mm radius spot. The absorbed energy ($\sim 0.1 \text{ }\mu\text{J}$) corresponded to a fluence of 0.27 J/cm^2 , well below the CFRP's ablation threshold, ensuring purely thermoelastic excitation [13]. A $20 \times 20 \text{ mm}^2$ region centred on each delamination was raster-scanned on a 195×195 grid with 0.103 mm pitch, yielding 38,025 excitation points (100 points/mm^2) per scan. The laser incidence angle was maintained below 2° , which is well within the $\sim 30^\circ$ tolerance for amplitude stability [14].

Out-of-plane displacements were measured using a broadband piezoelectric sensor (AE-900S-WB, frequency range 0.3–1.5 MHz, sensitivity $50 \text{ dB} \pm 6 \text{ dB}$ at 500 kHz). This sensor was mounted outside the laser scan region to prevent direct optical excitation. To characterize anisotropic wave propagation, the sensor was sequentially oriented along three directions relative to the 0° surface ply: PA (0°), PB (45°), and PC (90°). Each grid point was probed using four consecutive laser pulses, and the resulting signals were averaged to improve the signal-to-noise ratio while preserving bandwidth. Waveforms were sampled at 10 MS/s over a $100 \text{ }\mu\text{s}$ acquisition window, resulting in 1000 discrete amplitude measurements per waveform. This window was truncated $\sim 20 \text{ }\mu\text{s}$ before the expected A_0 -mode edge reflection, estimated using a $1.5 \text{ mm}/\mu\text{s}$ group velocity and 90 mm edge distance, to isolate the primary A_0 and S_0 wave packets from boundary reflections.

The dataset under consideration is comprised of 1,140,750 raw waveforms, distributed across ten plates, three sensor orientations, and 38,025 scan points per measurement. All signals were standardized using global Z-score normalization [15], defined as $x' = (x - \mu)/\sigma$, where μ and σ are the global mean and standard deviation across the dataset, respectively. This step equalized amplitude scales across signals, accelerated model convergence, and preserved waveform phase information.

2.2. CNN-Guided Hybrid Learning Framework

A hybrid learning framework has been developed that integrates a pre-trained lightweight 1D-CNN ($\sim 93,000$ parameters) with unsupervised clustering to identify latent delamination patterns in UGW data.

As illustrated in , the framework leverages physics-informed features learned from a limited labelled dataset to guide the discovery of physically meaningful structures within the high-dimensional feature space. Figure 1a illustrates the spatial region-based labelling strategy used to partition the 1D waveforms into a binary classification scheme, where signals originating from within the delaminated region are labelled as “damaged,” while those from outside this region are labelled as “undamaged”. Figure 1b shows a 1D-CNN pre-trained using a limited labelled dataset ($\sim 10\%$).

The SoftMax classification layer is removed from the 1D-CNN (Figure 1c), and the high-dimensional feature representations are extracted directly from the final dense layer. These features are then visualized in latent space, as shown in Figure 1d.

As illustrated in Figure 1e, several unsupervised clustering algorithms, including the proposed PCFC, are employed within the latent feature space to discern the underlying structure in the data. Finally, the clustering results are visualized both in the latent space and remapped onto the 2D wavefield (see Figure 1f), thereby providing a spatially interpretable representation of the detected patterns.

Figure 1: Overview of the hybrid learning framework. (a) region-based labelling separating undamaged and damaged waveforms; (b) 1D-CNN pre-trained on labelled data; (c) extracted high-level features; (d) visualization in latent space; (e) clustering using various algorithms; (f) analysis of clustering results.

2.3. Data Partitioning, Labelling, and Signal Preprocessing

A spatial region-based labelling strategy was adopted to pre-train the 1D-CNN using supervised learning. One damaged plate, representing approximately 10% of the total dataset, was selected as the reference for training. This plate contained a $5 \times 5 \text{ mm}^2$ artificial delamination embedded at the laminate midplane.

The corresponding wavefield, acquired using the LUVI-CP1 system, was represented as a three-dimensional matrix indexed by (x, y, t) . Let $\mathbf{r} = (x, y)$ denote a spatial location on the plate surface and let $w(\mathbf{r}, t)$ be the wave amplitude at position \mathbf{r} and time step t . At each scan point, the root mean square (RMS) amplitude, defined in Equation (1), was computed to highlight regions of elevated acoustic energy. To enhance contrast and delineate potential damage boundaries, the spatial gradient of the RMS amplitude map was then calculated, as shown in Equation (2). The resulting maps are illustrated in Figure 2a.

$$RMS(\mathbf{r}) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T w(\mathbf{r}, t)^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla RMS(\mathbf{r}) = \left(\frac{\partial RMS}{\partial r_1}, \frac{\partial RMS}{\partial r_2} \right) \quad (2)$$

Based on this processed representation, spatial masks were applied to assign coarse binary labels. Waveforms originating within the delaminated region were labelled “D” (delamination), and those outside were labelled “N” (non-delamination), as illustrated in Figure 2b. Following this region-based labelling, approximately 7,200 waveforms were identified as originating from delaminated regions, representing 6.25% of the labelled dataset. This class imbalance reflects the small physical extent of the delamination relative to the full scan area. To preserve the natural distribution of the data and prevent overfitting to plate-specific characteristics, no data augmentation was applied.

In total, this labelling procedure yielded 114,075 waveforms for supervised training. The remaining 1,026,675 waveforms, acquired from the other nine plates, formed the unlabelled pool used for unsupervised learning. All signals were standardized using global Z-score normalization and stored

alongside with categorical metadata indicating their source plate and spatial coordinates within the scan grid.

Figure 2: Two dimensional wavefield analyzed through RMS gradient (a) and with subsequent spatial-labelling mask applied (b).

2.4. Supervised Training of Lightweight 1D-CNN

A previously optimized shallow 1D-CNN architecture [11] was employed to perform supervised classification on the reduced, labelled dataset comprising 10% of the original data. The network begins with a single convolutional layer comprising 64 filters, each with a kernel size of 256. This is followed by batch normalization, a Parametric ReLU (PReLU) activation function, max pooling with a pooling size of 4, and a dropout layer with a rate of 20%. A global average pooling layer reduces the output to a 1×64 feature vector.

This vector is passed to a fully connected layer with 128 units. This is followed by a second dropout layer and a final dense layer with 2 output units, ending in a Softmax activation for classification. Weights were initialized using the Glorot normal scheme, and regularization techniques, including L1/L2 penalties and early stopping, were applied to improve generalization. The model was trained using the Adam optimizer with by a reduce-on-plateau scheduler handling learning rate adjustments.

The complete architecture contains approximately 93,000 trainable parameters, an order of magnitude fewer than typical 2D-CNN models, making it well suited to lightweight, real-time deployment. Training results, shown in Figure 3, demonstrate near-perfect classification accuracy with no observable signs of overfitting.

Figure 3: Supervised training results: (a) Training and Validation Accuracy, (b) Training and Validation Loss

2.5. Latent Feature Embedding and Cluster Number Estimation

To determine the optimal number of clusters k , a required parameter for many clustering algorithms, feature vectors were extracted from the penultimate dense layer of the pre-trained 1D-CNN when it was applied to the unseen dataset. This process yielded a 128-dimensional latent representation, thereby defining an encoder function $\varepsilon: \mathbb{R}^{1000} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{128}$. This function maps each input waveform \mathbf{x} to a latent vector $\mathbf{z} = \varepsilon(\mathbf{x}) \in \mathbb{R}^{128}$. In this latent space, intraclass variability is attenuated, while features relevant to delamination are accentuated, thereby facilitating more effective clustering.

In the context of unsupervised learning, the evaluation of clustering quality is of critical importance in ensuring that the discovered structures represent meaningful patterns rather than artifacts arising from noise or random variation. In contrast to the supervised learning, in which the performance of the model is evaluated against a known ground truth, the unsupervised clustering relies on internal validation metrics to assess the compactness, separation, and cohesion of the clusters. These metrics enable the evaluation of clustering effectiveness in the absence of labelled data, thereby providing a framework for guiding model selection and parameter tuning.

In scenarios where no prior knowledge of the underlying class structure is available, internal validation indices assume particular importance. These indices assess cluster quality based solely on the intrinsic geometric and statistical characteristics of the data. Nevertheless, they are not without limitations. A significant number of internal metrics implicitly assume isotropic, spherical cluster shapes and are based on Euclidean distance and centroid-based formulations. Consequently, the efficacy of such methods may be diminished when applied to data characterised by elongated, overlapping, or non-convex clusters, potentially resulting in erroneous assessments of clustering performance.

To address the limitations inherent in individual internal validation indices, it is common practice to employ multiple such metrics in parallel. This enables a more robust and comprehensive evaluation of clustering quality. Each index captures a distinct facet of the cluster structure, such as compactness, separation, or cohesion, thus offering complementary perspectives on the organization of the data. The following internal validation metrics were utilized in this study: Dunn Index, Calinski–Harabasz Index, Silhouette Score, Davies–Bouldin Index, and Xie–Beni Index. The optimal number of clusters was determined by applying a majority voting scheme, with consensus across the indices indicating that $k = 2$ provided the most appropriate partitioning. A summary of the computed metric values and comparative results is presented in Table 1.

Internal Validation Metric	Optimal k	Score
Dunn Index	2	0.65
Calinski-Harabasz index	4	165000
Silhouette Score	2	0.51
Davies-Bouldin index	4	0.71
Xie-Beni Index	2	0.18

Table 1: Optimal number of clusters calculated using different internal metrics.

2.6. Unsupervised Clustering Algorithms and Proposed PCFC Method

Five classical clustering algorithms were benchmarked on the extracted latent feature space:

- i. K-Means is a widely used partitioning algorithm that assigns data points to k clusters by minimizing within-cluster variance. It assumes spherical clusters of equal size and density.
- ii. GMM is an extension of K-Means that models the data as a mixture of Gaussian distributions. GMMs perform soft clustering by estimating the probability that each data point belongs to each cluster.
- iii. BGMM is a probabilistic generalization of GMMs that incorporates Bayesian inference. BGMMs treat the number of clusters and model parameters as random variables with prior distributions, allowing for automatic regularization and principled model selection.

- iv. DBSCAN is a non-parametric algorithm that identifies clusters as dense regions in the data space, separated by lower-density areas. It is effective to identify arbitrarily shaped clusters and identifying noise points, without the necessity of inputting the number of clusters.
- v. HDBSCAN is an extension of DBSCAN that builds a cluster hierarchy based on variable density thresholds. It removes the need to specify a global neighbourhood radius, making it more robust to datasets with varying local density.

In addition to these classical methods, a novel clustering approach, Probabilistic CNN-Fuzzy Clustering (PCFC), is proposed. PCFC integrates the discriminative feature extraction capabilities of a pre-trained 1D-CNN with the uncertainty modelling properties of the Fuzzy C-Means (FCM) algorithm. The 1D-CNN is employed to extract semantically meaningful representations from input signals, which are then passed through a SoftMax activation layer to generate probabilistic class assignments that reflect the underlying class structure learned during supervised training. Concurrently, FCM provides an unsupervised soft clustering mechanism, assigning each data point fractional membership across multiple clusters to capture uncertainty and gradual transitions between classes. The integration of the structured latent space generated by the CNN with the soft-partitioning behaviour of FCM facilitates effective clustering of PCFC in scenarios characterized by overlapping class boundaries and ambiguous data distributions.

Given an input sample x_i , the CNN generates class probability estimates via a SoftMax activation function, denoted as $p_{ij} = f_{CNN}^{Softmax}(x_i)$, where p_{ij} represents the predicted probability of sample i belonging to class j . To integrate these supervised predictions with fuzzy clustering, the PCFC framework introduces a hybrid membership function that combines the SoftMax output with fuzzy membership degrees computed in the CNN derived feature space. The hybrid membership degree \hat{u}_{ij} of sample i in cluster j is defined as:

$$\hat{u}_{ij} = \alpha \cdot u_{ij}(z_i) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot p_{ij}, \quad \text{with } 0 \leq \alpha \leq 1 \quad (3)$$

In Equation (3), $u_{ij}(z_i)$ denotes the fuzzy membership degree assigned by the FCM algorithm based on the CNN-extracted feature vector z_i , and p_{ij} is the previously defined SoftMax probability. The parameter α controls the trade-off between the unsupervised fuzzy clustering and the supervised probabilistic classification, thereby facilitating the integration of data-driven uncertainty with learned discriminative structure. This formulation enables PCFC to capitalize on both the representational power of CNNs and the uncertainty-aware nature of fuzzy clustering, thus resulting in a more robust and adaptable clustering framework.

To improve the physical interpretability and visual reliability of the PCFC results when projected onto the two-dimensional wavefield domain, the continuous hybrid membership values $\hat{u}_{ij} \in [0,1]$, interpreted here as degrees of delamination, are discretized into four semantically meaningful categories:

- Non-Delamination (N): $0 \leq \hat{u}_{ij} < 0.25$. Represents signals that closely match baseline (healthy) responses.
- Quasi-Non-Delamination (Q-N): $0.25 \leq \hat{u}_{ij} < 0.50$. Indicates largely intact regions exhibiting minor variations due to benign phenomena.
- Quasi-Delamination (Q-D): $0.50 \leq \hat{u}_{ij} < 0.75$. Captures partial or ambiguous indications of damage, which are frequently linked to scattering or boundary effects.
- Delamination (D): $0.75 \leq \hat{u}_{ij} \leq 1.00$. This is indicative of significant deviations from the baseline, which is consistent with the presence of structural damage.

This categorisation of continuous fuzzy outputs translates nuanced membership values into diagnostically meaningful labels, enhancing both the interpretability and practical utility of PCFC in SHM applications.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Spatial Analysis of Clustering Results

After clustering, the waveforms are mapped back onto the spatial grid to generate spatially resolved cluster maps, thereby enhancing visual interpretability of the results. In instances where clustering methods require a predefined number of clusters, the optimal value $k = 2$, as determined in Section 2.5., was employed.

Figure 4 presents a comparative evaluation of clustering performance on the training plate, with wave propagation along the PA direction. As illustrated in Figure 4a, K-Means provides a coarse distinction between delaminated and intact regions but lacks spatial precision. Figure 4b shows that GMM improves localization of damaged areas, however, the delineation of boundary regions remains ambiguous. BGMM offers enhanced isolation of the delaminated region and its boundaries. However, it introduces excessive clusters that do not correspond to physically meaningful structures (see Figure 4c). Figure 4d reveals that DBSCAN is unable to differentiate between damaged and undamaged regions, with the majority of data points being assigned to a dominant cluster. Figure 4e demonstrates that HDBSCAN partially mitigates this limitation by identifying three principal regions, undamaged, delaminated, and transitional. However, it should be noted that the resulting clusters lack clear physical interpretability in the absence of the full 2D wavefield context.

In contrast, Figure 4f demonstrates that PCFC yields a coherent and physically meaningful clustering outcome. Hybrid membership values in the range $0.75 \leq \hat{u}_{ij} < 1.00$ reliably indicate delamination, while values in the range $0.50 \leq \hat{u}_{ij} < 0.75$ capture transitional zones influenced by wave scattering and boundary effects. The lower ranges correspond to intact regions and propagation artefacts. The integration of CNN-derived features with fuzzy logic by PCFC has been demonstrated to achieve two objectives: Firstly, it facilitates accurate damage identification. Secondly, it establishes interpretable spatial representation. This combination of features establishes the PCFC framework as a robust solution for SHM.

The results of the clustering process for an unseen, undamaged laminate are shown in Figure 5, with wave propagation along the PC direction. These examples are intended to appraise the efficacy of each algorithm in generalising and accurately identifying the absence of damage in conditions that have not been previously observed. K-Means (Figure 5a) identifies two clusters that correspond visually to the wavefront and the remaining plate area. GMM (Figure 5b) produces a similar segmentation with only minor discrepancies in point allocation. BGMM (Figure 5c) exhibits similar tendencies to earlier observations, over-segmenting the data into multiple physically implausible clusters. DBSCAN and HDBSCAN (see Figure 5d-e) both identify a dominant single cluster, accurately reflecting the uniform, undamaged condition of the plate. This outcome supports their reliability in damage-free scenarios.

As illustrated in Figure 5f, PCFC yields a result resembling K-Means. However, a salient feature of PCFC is that it assigns all waveforms membership values in the range $0 \leq \hat{u}_{ij} < 0.50$, indicating absence of delamination. The plate's status as undamaged is confirmed by the hybrid metric, which enables effective differentiation between benign wavefront structures and damage-related features.

Figure 4: Clustering map analysis of the training plate with wave propagation PA, using: (a) K-Means, (b) GMM, (c) BGMM, (d) DBSCAN, (e) HDBSCAN, and (f) PCFC.

Figure 5 Clustering map analysis of an undamaged plate with wave propagation PC, using: (a) K-Means, (b) GMM, (c) BGMM, (d) DBSCAN, (e) HDBSCAN, and (f) PCFC.

3.2. Latent Feature Space Analysis via Principal Component Analysis

In addition to analysing clusters in remapped 2D wavefields, the latent feature space extracted by the 1D-CNN can be examined directly, independent of spatial context. The optimized network comprises a fully connected layer with 128 neurons, resulting in a high-dimensional representation that is not readily interpretable. In order to address this issue, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [16] is employed to

project the feature space onto a two-dimensional plane whilst preserving the most significant variance in the data.

As illustrated in Figure 6, PCA projections of the latent space for the test plate measured along the propagation direction PA are presented. This visualization facilitates a comparative assessment of clustering behaviour across algorithms. It is evident that both K-Means and GMM yield analogous cluster distributions, with K-Means separating clusters near zero and GMM shifting the boundary closer to -1 along the first principal component. The results of the BGMM are sparse, unstructured clusters that lack geometric coherence. DBSCAN and HDBSCAN fail to generate meaningful partitions, often resulting in the data being collapsed into a single dominant cluster or the production of irregular groupings.

In contrast, PCFC consistently yields well-separated and physically interpretable clusters. Waveforms with low hybrid membership values ($0 \leq \hat{u}_{ij} < 0.25$) are located on the positive side of the first principal component, whereas those with high membership values ($0.75 \leq \hat{u}_{ij} \leq 1.00$) are concentrated around -2.5 to -3 . This consistent pattern across datasets suggests a robust correspondence between the first principal component and damage severity. Specifically, waveforms from undamaged regions have a tendency to cluster in the positive domain, while those from delaminated regions map to the negative extreme, thereby providing a distinctive signature of structural integrity in composite laminates.

Figure 6: Feature space clustering analysis of the training plate with wave propagation PA, using: (a) K-Means, (b) GMM, (c) BGMM, (d) DBSCAN, (e) HDBSCAN, and (f) PCFC.

3.3. Effect of CNN Pre-training on Clustering Performance

To demonstrate the benefits of pre-training the 1D-CNN feature extractor, particularly in scenarios with limited labelled data, the clustering results of 2D remapped wavefields using K-Means are presented here. Figure 7 compares outputs for two laminates containing a 10×10 mm² delamination at different depths (0.84 mm and 0.56 mm) with wave propagation direction PA. Figure 7a–b show cluster maps from an untrained model, while Figure 7c–d illustrate the enhanced performance achieved with the pre-trained feature extractor.

Figure 7: K-Means clustering comparison between an untrained (a, c) and pre-trained (b, d) 1D-CNN model with the same architecture, applied to plate two plates with $10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$ delaminations located at 0.56 mm depth (a, b) and 0.84 mm depth (c, d), respectively.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduced a hybrid supervised–unsupervised learning framework designed to enable physically meaningful cluster analysis on unseen data, using only limited labelled input. Whilst the clustering itself lacks explicit physical interpretability, this limitation was addressed by incorporating a pre-trained 1D-CNN as an optimized feature extractor.

The 1D-CNN was trained on waveforms acquired from a single CFRP plate using the LUVI system. The reciprocity theorem was utilised to map these 1D measurements into 2D wavefields and to label them as “delamination” or “non-delamination” for supervised training. Following the completion of the training process, the CNN was able to extract low-dimensional feature representations from new, unlabelled datasets. This enabled clustering in a compact, discriminative space.

A comparative analysis of clustering algorithms (K-Means, GMM, BGMM, DBSCAN, HDBSCAN, and the proposed PCFC) was conducted on this embedded feature space. The proposed PCFC, which combines CNN-derived probabilities with fuzzy membership values from FCM, demonstrated consistent superiority in terms of accuracy and physical interpretability when compared to alternative methods. The visual representation of the damage was clear, and there was a strong alignment with the actual structural conditions. In contrast, DBSCAN failed to identify damaged regions, while BGMM, despite demonstrating effective segmentation performance, suffered from excessive granularity and high computational cost.

An important observation emerged from the feature space distribution: clusters associated with delamination consistently mapped to the negative axis of the first principal component (PC1), starting near -2.5 , while undamaged regions aligned with the positive PC1 axis. This trend suggests a potentially generalizable indicator of delamination in unseen waveforms.

In summary, the proposed approach provides a robust, data-efficient solution for the detection of delamination, especially valuable when fully supervised datasets are not available.

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